

STRATEGIC FRAMEWORK FOR SOCIALLY RESPONSIBLE UNIVERSITIES IN THE ERA OF MIGRATION

THE UNI(di)VERSITY STRATEGIC FRAMEWORK

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ABOUT UNI(DI)VERSITY

UNI(di)VERSITY aims to support European Higher Education Institutions to uphold their role towards **building inclusive societies in the era of migration**, with a view to promoting the **social inclusion of migrants and refugees**. The project is funded by the Erasmus+ programme of the European Union during the period January 2020 – December 2022.

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INTRODUCTION

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The Strategic Framework is a methodological instrument designed to support the university leaders (Rectors, Vice-Rectors, Deans...) in their effort to further develop and strengthen the strategy for inclusion of their Higher Education Institutions (HEI). In particular, the Strategic Framework is intended to empower HEIs to adopt a holistic institutional approach to the migration phenomenon, and to support the dissemination of such to a broader audience, notably, key stakeholders operating in the fields of migration and Higher Education (HE).

The Framework addresses five key dimensions that should be embedded when setting up and implementing socially responsible policies, strategies, and initiatives in relation to the migration phenomenon.

The five dimensions include four horizontal dimensions: political, administrative, social, and financial, and the transversal dimension of awareness. For each dimension, the rationale for its incorporation is outlined and illustrations are provided from the Atlas of Inclusion.

Moreover, links to the related Toolkit instrument are suggested.

In this way, the Strategic Framework is intended as a summary of key dimensions that have emerged from the different outputs of the project.

INFOGRAPHIC

1. AWARENESS DIMENSION

AWARENESS DIMENSION

Awareness of the perceived and current state of the art of the institution's maturity level in relation to migration-related issues is essential to the development of a tailor-made approach to diversity and inclusion.

Understanding strengths and weaknesses of the institutional work on migration and inclusion is a fundamental precondition for further developing ideas and actions to promote equity, diversity, and inclusion in relation to migration.

Field practices

Several universities are involved in awareness-raising amongst the university community and in the general population, with the aim of changing the narrative around forced migration and refugees.

For instance, the universities of Malmo (SE), Roma La Sapienza (IT), Aegean (EL), Gottingen (DE), Maastricht (NL) and Zurich (CH), offer cultural exchanges, sport events, and other integration activities involving both the local population and migrants with a refugee(-like) background, irrespective of whether or not they are potential students.

1. AWARENESS Dimension

Object:	Field Practices	Link to Toolkit
<p>Referred to the perceived and current state of the art of the institution's maturity level in relation to migrant-related issues.</p> <p style="text-align: center; margin-top: 10px;">Purpose:</p> <p>Understanding strengths, weaknesses, challenges and opportunities.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A Research activities B Actions aimed at changing the narrative around forced migration and refugees C Monitoring 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A Institutional maturity on diversity and inclusion self-assessment tool: self-positioning among different scenarios B Governance Diagnostic Tool: perception of the style of governance in terms of migration and inclusion C Interview and focus groups' guides: identification of needs, expectations, challenges and opportunities of internal and external stakeholders D Policy canva: analysis of the state of the art and actions

Link to the toolkit

The dimension of awareness is cross-sectional, precisely because of its anticipatory nature for the purposes of any activity aimed at the inclusion and enhancement of diversity in the university.

In particular, this dimension emerges with greatest force in the GDT in the section *Framing migration and diversity in the mission and values of the organisation (GDT1)*, *Self-awareness on unconscious biases at decision-making levels and their impact on policies, strategies and actions (GDT4)*, *Design and implementation of inclusive policies on migration (GDT5)*, and *Migration and inclusion. Accessibility and retention policies (GDT6¹)*. Moreover, the interview's and focus group guide offers a set of questions that can be used in order to better analyse the perceived and current state of the art of the HEI in relation to diversity and inclusion.

1) **GDT1.** Are Inclusion and diversity key parts of your institution fundamental documents? For instance, is inclusion and diversity mentioned explicitly in some of the following documents? a. Mission and vision b. Institutional Strategies or Action Plans c. Communication strategies (internal and external communication) d. Recruitment and retention strategies (for students, administrative staff and teachers/researchers).

B Is there a specific mention/specific action related to the topic of migration in the documents related to inclusion and diversity?

Are there specific human resources and budget allocated to work on actions/strategies related to the topic of migration?

GDT4. Are there mechanisms of identification of biases and self-biases on the topic of migration and inclusion at the level of the governing bodies?

Has there been analysis, research or training on the impact of biases and self-biases on the topic at the level of the governing bodies?

Are there actions identified in order to prevent the negative impact of biases and self-biases in terms of inclusion/diversity topics in decision-making levels?

GDT5. Does the organisation have specific tools or policies addressed to identify and meet the socio-academic needs of migrant/refugee background people (students, staff)?

Does the organisation have a strategy to reach out and promote the involvement and participation of migrant/refugee background communities in the design, implementation, monitoring and evaluation of inclusion and diversity policies? If so, what are the indicators that allow to measure the achievement or progress in terms of migration and inclusion?

Does the organisation have a policy of transparency and publicise the results of the inclusion and diversity policies in the area of migration?

GDT6.

Does the organisation have a specific policy (or in the general policy foresees for migrant and refugees as well) for improving the access to the University studies and job positions taking into account the particular challenges of this group? Example, in the case of access to studies of migrant/refugee migrant students, is the HEI coordinating actions of mentoring or scholarships addressed to this community? Is working as well with primary and secondary schools to inform and encourage pupils to enrol at the University?

Are the different actions of the organisation well known by the university community? Are these actions coordinated in order to maximise their impact?

Does the organisation foreseen specific actions to promote retention and success of migrant/refugee background people in their studies and job positions?

Does the university community receive training on intercultural competences, intercultural communication, etc

2. POLITICAL DIMENSION

POLITICAL DIMENSION

The political dimension refers to the HEI mission and values.

The involvement of the scientific community and its commitment to concrete and binding actions is an essential precondition for ensuring the diversity strategy's long-term sustainability.

Field practices

Specific reference to the target group of refugees, or migrants in a refugee(-like) situation, is included in the diversity and inclusion strategy of the Universities of Trento (IT) and Utrecht (NL). Other universities refer to various central-level documents linked to the support of migrants in a refugee(-like) situation without mentioning refugees explicitly.

For instance, this is the case of the Universities of Malmö, Barcelona and Roma La Sapienza. The first covers the theme of diversity and inclusion in both its Strategy 2022 and its Agenda for Global Engagement.

The second has aligned its central Strategic Plan with the UN's Global Compact for Refugees (United Nations, 2018) and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

Sapienza University links to diversity in its central statutes and is a signatory to the High Commissioner for Refugees' Manifesto of the Inclusive University (UNHCR, 2019).

Link to the toolkit

Regarding the political dimension, the toolkit offers valuable reference points concerning both the *Institutional Maturity on diversity and inclusion self-assessment tool* (IM) and the *Governance Diagnostic Tool* (GDT).

Moreover, the toolkit includes a guide to interview or develop focus groups with defined stakeholders in order to identify the mission and value of the organisation. With respect to the Institutional Maturity tool, particular reference to the political dimension can be found in the area of *governance* (IM_G1, IM_G4, IM_G6, ¹), in the area of *access to the university* (IM_AU1²) as well as in the area of *"Supporting migrants/refugees during their university years"* (SM3³).

Concerning the Governance Diagnostic Tool (GDT), the relevance of the political dimension emerges both with regard to the section on *Framing migration and diversity in the mission and values of*

1) **IM_G1.** The governance body of the University considers that diversity and inclusion of migrants and refugees is a topic to work during their mandate

IM_G4. There is an action plan to carry out specific actions to improve diversity and inclusion at the University

IM_G6. The University regularly publishes the goals and outcomes in terms of diversity and inclusion of migrants/refugees

2) **IM_AU1.** The Organisation has a knowledge -based on qualitative or quantitative information- regarding the main obstacles of migrant/refugee students to access the university

3) **SM3.** The University encourages the adoption of universal design for addressing different learning styles and personal situations.

the organization (GDT1⁴), and that of *Self-awareness on unconscious biases at decision-making levels and their impact on policies, strategies and actions* (GDT4⁵) as well as *Migration and inclusion. accessibility and retention policies* (GDT6⁶).

4) **GDT1**. A. Are Inclusion and diversity key parts of your institution fundamental documents? For instance, is inclusion and diversity mentioned explicitly in some of the following documents? a. Mission and vision b. Institutional Strategies or Action Plans c. Communication strategies (internal and external communication) d. Recruitment and retention strategies (for students, administrative staff and teachers/researchers).
B. Is there a specific mention/specific action related to the topic of migration in the documents related to inclusion and diversity?

5) **GDT4** Are there mechanisms of identification of biases and self-biases on the topic of migration and inclusion at the level of the governing bodies?
Has there been analysis, research or training on the impact of biases and self-biases on the topic at the level of the governing bodies?
Are there actions identified in order to prevent the negative impact of biases and self-biases in terms of inclusion/diversity topics in decision-making levels?

6) **GDT6** Does the organisation have a specific policy (or in the general policy foresees for migrant and refugees as well) for improving the access to the University studies and job positions taking into account the particular challenges of this group? Example, in the case of access to studies of migrant/refugee migrant students, is the HEI coordinating actions of mentoring or scholarships addressed to this community? Is working as well with primary and secondary schools to inform and encourage pupils to enrol at the University?
Are the different actions of the organisation well known by the university community? Are these actions coordinated in order to maximise their impact?
Does the organisation foreseen specific actions to promote retention and success of migrant/refugee background people in their studies and job positions
Does the university community receive training on intercultural competences, intercultural communication, etc

3. ADMINISTRATIVE DIMENSION

ADMINISTRATIVE DIMENSION

The administrative dimension refers to the internal organisation of the university, in terms of the availability of offices dedicated to the diversity management and services provided.

The provision of comprehensive services is a key condition for higher education participation and it is particularly important for those from disadvantaged backgrounds, such as migrants with a refugee (-like) background. It is crucial to take into account refugees' specific personal situations due to their legal status, their psychosocial circumstances and their social situation as well as to match study opportunities to the students' abilities and expectations.

Field practices

Several institutions have dedicated admissions services and special recognition procedures for admission purposes in place for applicants with a refugee(-like) background (Universities of Ghent (BE), Malmo (SE), Roma Sapienza (IT) Libre de Bruxelles (BE), Barcelona (ES), Jyvaskyla (FI), Trento (IT), and Utrecht (NL).

Other institutions have a diversity office, or at least one diversity officer, that supports all disadvantaged learners, including migrants with a refugee(-like) background. For instance, at the University of Trento, representatives of the different university departments cooperate with the Vice-Rector for Equity and Diversity Policies and the Equality & Diversity Office

Link to the toolkit

The administrative dimension is particularly emphasised in the Toolkit: among the areas of the IM we find numerous best practices suggested in the *Governance* area (IM_G2¹), the *Staff* area (IM_S1, IM_S2, IM_S3²), the *access to the University* area (IM_AU2³) and the *Supporting migrants/refugees during their university years* area (SM5, SM6⁴). Also, in the GDT there is a reference (GDT1⁵) to the allocation of human resources to work on actions/strategies related to the topic of migration.v

1) **IM_G2.** The governance body of the University has designated a position to work on inclusion of migrants and refugees

2) **IM_S1.** University staff receives information related to diversity and inclusion activities at the University
IM_S2. University staff receive training on intercultural competence, cultural codes, conflict management, anti-harassment legislation, etc. IM_S3. The University staff composition is diverse in terms of representation of the local community

3) **IM_AU2.** The University has tools for facilitating the recognition of prior studies of migrant/refugee students

4) **SM5.** The university encourages internships that are compatible with the administrative status and mobility of migrant/refugee students SM6. The university supports refugee/migrant students in their access to job market through offering internship opportunities, support in designing CV

5) **GDT1 C.** Are there specific human resources and budget allocated to work on actions/strategies related to the topic of migration?

4. FINANCIAL DIMENSION

FINANCIAL DIMENSION

The financial dimension refers to the allocation of budget to undertake concrete and effective actions to realise the transformative capacity of the university.

The presence of a defined and appropriate budget enables the planning of short- and long-term objectives, assuring the sustainability of intended actions.

Field practices

The Universities of Ghent (BE), Trento (IT), Utrecht (NL) and Grenoble (FR) provide study funds for asylum seekers and grants for refugees. Moreover, in addition to scholarships, many universities invest part of their budget in order to support services for refugee students in a variety of ways.

For instance, the Université Libre de Bruxelles provides financial support for exams and language lessons for refugees and established a solidarity fund for researchers at risk.

Link to the toolkit

The financial dimension appears in the toolkit in both the section on the *IM*, in the areas of the *Governance* (IM_G5¹) and in the one on *Supporting migrants/refugees during their university years* (SM2²), and as well in the *Governance Diagnostic Tool* (GDT) in the sections *Framing migration and diversity in the mission and values of the organization* (GDT1³) and *Funding and human resources* (GT7⁴). Moreover, the interview's and focus group guide draw attention to the budget allocation in determining the effectiveness of migrant inclusion actions. Finally, a particular section for the financial and human resources is included in the policy canvas. v

1 **IM_G5.** There are appropriate financial and human resources to develop actions related to diversity and inclusionPolicy canvas: The canvas has a particular section for the financial and human resources

2 **SM2.** The University has scholarships aimed at supporting migrant/refugees with low incomes

3 **GDT1.** C. Are there specific human resources and budget allocated to work on actions/strategies related to the topic of migration?

4 **GT7.** Do the policies and actions on migration and inclusion identified above have a reasonable funding and human resources allocation?

5. SOCIAL DIMENSION

SOCIAL DIMENSION

The social dimension encompasses both the university's relationship with other institutions and the implementation by the university of actions aimed at fostering inclusion.

The creation of links at peer-to-peer level and with the host context is essential for the achievement of an effective inclusion strategy.

The inclusion and enhancement of different ways of knowing also passes through the representation of the plurality of knowledge of students, administrative staff and academics that make up the university community. In this sense the university could potentially act as a bridge towards social networking and employment inclusion.

Field practices

Buddy, mentoring or coaching programmes are implemented at the universities of Ghent (BE), Maastricht (NL), Rome Sapienza (IT), Barcelona (ES), Zurich (CH) and Utrecht (NL). All these universities, plus Malmö (SE), Göttingen (DE), Aegean (EL), and Jyväskylä (FI), also offer language courses for migrant and refugee(like) students, in certain cases as a part of an overall bridging course.

Grenoble School of Management (FR) organises Career Booster workshops aimed at helping refugees to understand the French job market and collaborate with local stakeholders in order to help work placement.

5. SOCIAL Dimension

Object:

Refers both the **university's relationship with other institutions** and the implementation by the university of **actions aimed at fostering inclusion**.

Purpose:

Creation of **links at peer-to-peer level** and with the host context

Field Practices

A Buddy, mentoring or coaching programmes

C Career Booster Workshops aimed at helping refugees to understand the French job market

B Language courses for migrant and refugee(-like) students

Link to Toolkit

1 Institutional Maturity on diversity and inclusion self-assessment tool (IM)

- Improving access IM_AU3
- Retention actions IM_SM1
- Support the transition to the job market IM_SM6

2 Interview and Focus Group Guide suggestions from stakeholders

3 Policy Canva identification of good practices and main actions to be

Link to the toolkit

The fundamental importance of the social dimension is particularly underlined in the IM, in the areas of the *access in the University* (IM_AU3¹) and in the one on “*Supporting migrants/refugees during their university years*” (SM1, SM5, SM6²).

The interview’s and focus group guide also help to identify strategies or good practices that contribute to supporting the sense of belonging to the University community for migrant/refugee background people.

1) **IM_AU3.** The University works jointly with local authorities, secondary schools, NGOS and/or rest of the civil society for improving the access of migrant/Refugee students to the University through different actions, for instance, accompaniment, meetings with role model students, etc

2) **SM1.** The Organisation has buddy programmes and/or tutorial plans aimed at promoting the retention of migrant/refugee students, in particular, in the first years
SM5. The university encourages internships that are compatible with the administrative status and mobility of migrant/refugee students
SM6. The university supports refugee/migrant students in their access to job market through offering internship opportunities, support in designing CV

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